

Analytical Report

Sample data report

New Mexico Bureau of Geology
and Mineral Resources

801 Leroy Place
Socorro, NM 87801
(575) 835-5160
(575) 835-5416

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4260	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	239	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	95.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	24.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	15.4	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	628	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.65	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	---------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.457	mg/L	10	0.005	(0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01	(0.1)	4/2/2020
Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.195	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.012	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	14.5	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.59	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0127	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	0.0078	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
---	------------------------------------	------------------------------	-----------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.67	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Chloride	884	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/7/2020
Fluoride	1.97	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Nitrate	3.13	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/7/2020
Sulfate	889	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/7/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	---------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	242	mg/L	1	5	4/1/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	296	mg/L	1	5	4/1/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	48.51	meq/L	1		
Cations total	47.74	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.80	%	1		
SiO2	31.1	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2950	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	990	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4300	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	241	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	93.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	24.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	14.7	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	615	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.60	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	---------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.466	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.197	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.012	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	14.2	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.65	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0127	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	0.0077	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	---------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.67	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Chloride	882	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/7/2020
Fluoride	1.97	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Nitrate	2.31	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/7/2020
Sulfate	887	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	---------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	264	mg/L	1	5	4/1/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	322	mg/L	1	5	4/1/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/1/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	48.82	meq/L	1		
Cations total	47.06	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.84	%	1		
SiO2	30.4	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2940	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	986	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4310	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	244	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	94.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	25.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	12.9	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	619	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.60	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	---------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.496	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.200	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.012	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	13.5	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.64	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0127	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	0.0078	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	---------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.58	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Chloride	883	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/7/2020
Fluoride	1.98	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Nitrate	1.23	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/7/2020
Sulfate	883	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	---------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	260	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	317	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	48.65	meq/L	1		
Cations total	47.53	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.16	%	1		
SiO2	28.9	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2950	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	999	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4240	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	243	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	93.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	24.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	12.6	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	620	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.61	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	---------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.017	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.493	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.208	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.012	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	13.0	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.63	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0127	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	0.0075	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	---------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.55	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Chloride	869	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/7/2020
Fluoride	1.96	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/7/2020
Sulfate	868	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	---------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	260	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	318	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	47.96	meq/L	1		
Cations total	47.48	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.50	%	1		
SiO2	27.8	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2910	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	994	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4240	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	239	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	91.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	23.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	11.7	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	602	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.50	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	---------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.016	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.499	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.196	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.013	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	12.4	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.55	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0125	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	0.0072	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	---------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.60	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Chloride	876	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/7/2020
Fluoride	1.99	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/7/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/7/2020
Sulfate	878	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	---------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	270	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	329	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	48.55	meq/L	1		
Cations total	46.28	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.39	%	1		
SiO2	26.5	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2910	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	975	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-06	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	2060	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-06	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-06	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	123	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	45.6	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	15.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	13.6	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	272	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.25	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-06	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.044	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.243	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.094	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	14.2	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.24	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-06	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	--------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.18	mg/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Chloride	328	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/7/2020
Fluoride	1.23	mg/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	4/7/2020
Sulfate	348	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-06	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	--------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	268	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	319	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-06	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	21.91	meq/L	1		
Cations total	22.11	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.46	%	1		
SiO2	30.4	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1330	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-06	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	494	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-07	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	2070	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-07	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-07	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	124	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	45.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	14.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	13.6	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	269	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.24	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-07	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.040	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.243	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.093	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	14.2	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.28	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-07	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	--------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.17	mg/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Chloride	329	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/7/2020
Fluoride	1.27	mg/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	4/7/2020
Sulfate	350	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-07	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	--------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	270	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	326	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-07	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	22.03	meq/L	1		
Cations total	21.98	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.12	%	1		
SiO2	30.4	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1330	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-07	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	494	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-08	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	2120	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-08	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-08	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	124	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	44.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	14.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	13.3	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	265	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.21	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-08	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.036	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.240	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.094	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	13.6	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.30	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-08	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	--------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.15	mg/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Chloride	335	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/7/2020
Fluoride	1.24	mg/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	4/7/2020
Sulfate	351	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-08	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	--------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	272	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	325	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-08	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	22.27	meq/L	1		
Cations total	21.81	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.05	%	1		
SiO2	29.2	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1330	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-08	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	495	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-09	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	2130	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-09	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-09	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	133	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	47.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	15.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	14.3	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	274	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.29	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-09	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.029	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.243	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.097	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.017	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	14.7	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.32	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-09	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	--------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.18	mg/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Chloride	344	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/7/2020
Fluoride	1.27	mg/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	4/7/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	4/7/2020
Sulfate	363	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-09	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	--------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	270	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	329	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-09	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	22.73	meq/L	1		
Cations total	22.81	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.19	%	1		
SiO2	31.4	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1380	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-09	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	525	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-10	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	2170	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-10	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-10	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	134	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	47.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	15.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	14.0	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	283	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.37	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-10	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.031	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.248	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	0.0055	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.094	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	14.5	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.36	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	0.0098	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-10	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	--------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.20	mg/L	1	0.1	4/8/2020
Chloride	348	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/8/2020
Fluoride	1.27	mg/L	1	0.1	4/8/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	4/8/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	4/8/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	4/8/2020
Sulfate	364	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-10	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	--------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	276	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	337	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-10	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	23.01	meq/L	1		
Cations total	23.35	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.72	%	1		
SiO2	31.1	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1400	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-10	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	533	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-11	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3240	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-11	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.1	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-11	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	172	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	78.6	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	18.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	8.89	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	439	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.40	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-11	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.383	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.152	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	9.45	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.42	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	0.0137	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-11	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	--------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Chloride	634	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020
Fluoride	1.63	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/8/2020
Sulfate	650	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-11	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	--------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	225	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	275	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-11	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.01	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.59	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.01	%	1		
SiO2	20.2	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2150	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-11	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	752	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-12	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3220	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-12	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-12	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	164	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	77.6	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	18.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	9.06	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	436	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.35	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-12	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.385	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.150	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	9.47	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.45	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-12	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	--------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.54	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Chloride	638	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020
Fluoride	1.67	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrate	0.55	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/8/2020
Sulfate	656	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-12	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	--------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	211	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	251	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-12	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.96	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.00	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.79	%	1		
SiO2	20.3	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2140	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-12	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	728	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-13	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3230	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-13	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-13	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	172	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	80.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	19.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	9.12	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	446	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.44	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-13	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.384	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.152	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	9.65	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.47	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0055	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-13	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	--------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Chloride	641	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020
Fluoride	1.66	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrate	0.53	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/8/2020
Sulfate	659	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-13	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	--------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	222	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	267	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-13	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.32	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.05	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.78	%	1		
SiO2	20.6	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-13	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	760	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-14	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3230	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-14	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-14	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	175	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	81.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	19.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	9.04	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	457	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.53	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-14	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.382	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.152	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	9.35	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.46	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0055	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	0.0057	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-14	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	--------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Chloride	639	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020
Fluoride	1.72	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/8/2020
Sulfate	654	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-14	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	--------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	221	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	264	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-14	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.23	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.77	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.64	%	1		
SiO2	20.0	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2190	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-14	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	770	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-15	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3240	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-15	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-15	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	175	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	78.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	18.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	8.79	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	440	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.41	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-15	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.383	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.158	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	9.63	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.52	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	0.0074	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-15	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	--------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Chloride	631	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020
Fluoride	1.75	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/8/2020
Sulfate	645	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-15	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	--------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	222	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	271	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-15	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.77	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.87	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.27	%	1		
SiO2	20.6	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2150	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-15	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	763	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-16	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3260	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-16	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	--------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-16	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	171	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	78.6	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	18.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	8.90	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	446	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.46	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-16	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.384	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.150	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	9.53	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.50	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	0.0145	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-16	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	--------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Chloride	639	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020
Fluoride	1.77	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrate	0.57	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/8/2020
Sulfate	656	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-16	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	--------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	226	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	273	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-16	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	--------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.36	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.90	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.05	%	1		
SiO2	20.4	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-16	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	--------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	751	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-17	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3260	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-17	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.0	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-17	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	177	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	80.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	19.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.1	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	450	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.47	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-17	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	---------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.385	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.149	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.7	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.49	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0057	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	0.0113	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-17	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	---------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Chloride	639	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020
Fluoride	1.56	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/8/2020
Sulfate	656	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-17	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	---------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	215	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	262	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-17	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.13	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.49	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.90	%	1		
SiO2	22.9	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-17	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	772	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-18	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3250	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-18	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-18	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	180	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	80.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	19.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.4	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	445	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.47	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-18	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	---------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.020	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.386	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.150	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	11.1	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.53	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0057	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-18	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	---------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Chloride	637	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020
Fluoride	1.60	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrate	0.51	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/8/2020
Sulfate	654	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-18	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	---------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	220	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	264	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-18	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.08	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.50	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.81	%	1		
SiO2	23.8	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-18	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	783	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-19	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3250	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-19	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-19	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	182	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	79.6	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	19.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.3	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	440	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.46	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-19	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	---------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.372	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.155	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.8	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.54	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-19	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	---------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Chloride	638	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020
Fluoride	1.61	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/8/2020
Sulfate	655	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-19	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	---------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	228	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	274	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-19	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.27	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.27	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.41	%	1		
SiO2	23.1	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-19	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	782	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-20	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3230	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-20	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-20	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	183	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	80.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	19.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.2	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	439	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.44	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-20	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	---------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.386	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.147	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.9	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.50	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0057	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-20	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	---------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Chloride	636	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020
Fluoride	1.64	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrate	0.61	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/8/2020
Sulfate	653	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-20	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	---------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	230	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	281	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-20	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.26	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.34	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.29	%	1		
SiO2	23.4	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-20	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	788	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-21	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3260	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-21	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-21	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	183	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	79.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	19.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.3	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	446	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.49	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-21	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	---------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.022	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.381	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.151	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.9	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.51	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	0.0083	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-21	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	---------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Chloride	638	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020
Fluoride	1.58	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrate	0.54	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/8/2020
Sulfate	654	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-21	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	---------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	231	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	282	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-21	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.36	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.55	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.13	%	1		
SiO2	23.2	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2190	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-21	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	783	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-22	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3260	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-22	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.1	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-22	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	184	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	80.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	19.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.3	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	448	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.48	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-22	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	---------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.384	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.149	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.7	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.55	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	0.0103	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-22	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	---------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Chloride	638	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020
Fluoride	1.60	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/8/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/8/2020
Sulfate	658	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-22	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	---------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	231	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	282	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-22	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.46	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.79	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.93	%	1		
SiO2	22.8	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2200	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-22	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	791	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-23	Customer sample ID: Saragosa Spring #2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	---	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	2230	uS/cm	1		4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-23	Customer sample ID: Saragosa Spring #2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	---	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	7.9	ph Units	1		4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-23	Customer sample ID: Saragosa Spring #2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	---	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	137	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	48.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	15.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	14.0	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	292	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.38	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-23	Customer sample ID: Saragosa Spring #2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	---	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Barium	0.035	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/2/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Boron 11	0.274	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Lithium	0.103	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Silicon	15.3	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/2/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.47	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/2/2020
Uranium	0.0055	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-23	Customer sample ID: Saragosa Spring #2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	---	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	1	0.1	4/8/2020
Chloride	371	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/8/2020
Fluoride	1.40	mg/L	1	0.1	4/8/2020
Nitrate	2.78	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	4/8/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	4/8/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	4/8/2020
Sulfate	384	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-23	Customer sample ID: Saragosa Spring #2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	---	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	268	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	327	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	4/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200315
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/30/2020 12:29:55 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-23	Customer sample ID: Saragosa Spring #2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	---	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	23.96	meq/L	1		
Cations total	23.91	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.11	%	1		
SiO2	32.7	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1450	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200315-23	Customer sample ID: Saragosa Spring #2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	---	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	542	mg CaCO3/ L	1		